

Business based on bamboo arts and crafts products in east Lombok

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Abstract

This research aims to find out the process of making bamboo crafts in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok, to find out the materials and tools used to make bamboo crafts in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok and to find out what types of bamboo woven crafts there are in the village. Loyok, Sikur, East Lombok. The data collection techniques used in this research are observation, interview and documentation techniques. The results of the research obtained by the researchers were knowing the process of making bamboo crafts in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok, the types of woven bamboo craft products in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok are *Ponjol, Lompak, And Dedungki*, and the process of making woven bamboo crafts is the process of selecting bamboo and processing bamboo, namely felling bamboo, cutting bamboo, slicing bamboo, painting bamboo slices and nembeq.

Keywords: Crafts; Bamboo Weaving; Art Products; Tourist Villages

1. Introduction

There are many kinds of art and culture that have developed in Indonesia, one of which is bamboo woven crafts. Bamboo woven crafts are not something new in arts and culture in Indonesian society, but are cultural riches that have been inherited from generation to generation. Nowadays, the existence of science and technology has shifted the position of bamboo in people's lives, replaced by plastic which is very unfriendly to the environment. However, this fact does not mean that woven bamboo items have lost their fans because in the current era there are people who have converted bamboo woven crafts from their original function in the sense of making them into decoration.

In Indonesia, there are many regions that produce various types of woven bamboo products. One of the areas producing bamboo chicken is Loyok Village. This woven bamboo craft made in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok consists of various types of products that are produced but are not yet known to the wider community. Therefore, it is very necessary to carry out further research regarding the types and processes of making woven bamboo crafts in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok. Through this qualitative research, it is hoped that we will be able to describe the processes, tools and materials as well as types of bamboo weaving crafts in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok in order to preserve cultural heritage.

2. Methods

If this research is viewed based on its explanation, it is classified as a type of qualitative research. Qualitative research is also called naturalistic research because the research is carried out in natural conditions. Furthermore, qualitative research is also called interpretive research because research data is more concerned with interpretation (opinions, interpretations) of data found in the field.

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The aim of this descriptive qualitative research is to create systematic, factual and accurate descriptions, images or paintings regarding the types and processes of making woven bamboo craft products in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok. In collecting data, the author uses observation, interview and documentation techniques in order to obtain accurate data or information in accordance with the problem formulation and research objectives so as to obtain more in-depth data.

3. Result and discussion

Bamboo crafts are one of the creative industries in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok which has very high artistic and cultural value and is popular with many tourists, both local and foreign. Bamboo woven crafts in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok Village have been carried out for generations, no one knows for sure since what year the people started making these crafts. Bamboo woven crafts in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok are one source of livelihood for the residents there. Based on observations, most of the woven craft makers in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok are people who are no longer productive working in the rice fields. The creation of unique crafts with high selling value is a substitute for the income that should be obtained from working in the fields because in general the people in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok are farmers. Furthermore, the existence of this bamboo woven craft has a positive impact on people who are no longer able to be productive due to age but must continue to work to meet their family's needs. In the past, bamboo crafts in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok only produced household utensils, but now bamboo crafts in the area have increasingly developed and become unique objects to be used as souvenirs.

In the process of making woven bamboo crafts in Loyok village, there are several processes that need to be paid attention to, including the process of selecting bamboo. The bamboo used as material is not just any bamboo, but bamboo which already has finer fibers than the usual type of bamboo. This type of bamboo is called rope bamboo, this term emerged because when this type of bamboo was sliced and made into rope. The strength of this bamboo is partly because this type of bamboo has fine fibers, if this bamboo rope has a higher age it will have lower strength. If you use bamboo that is too young, it is also not good, because if it is split and dried in the sun, it will shrink so it is not good for use in making woven material. So, bamboo that is good for use as woven material is bamboo that has characteristics such as appearing yellow in color, there are several petals attached to the stem, this indicates that the bamboo is ready to be cut and made into woven material.

Then, in the bamboo processing process, there are several stages that are carried out, namely the first is felling and cutting the bamboo. First, the bamboo that has been selected is cut down and the branches are cleaned, then cut and the parts that will be used are taken. Second, the process of cutting bamboo is the first process in making woven bamboo crafts. The bamboo that has been selected will be cut using a saw, then split using a machete, and cleaned with a scraper or *maje*. Then the bamboo is split into several pieces of the required size.

The next process is that the bamboo has been split into parts, then the inside contents are removed, then the bamboo is ready to be sliced. This process can be said to be quite a difficult stage, because this slicing process requires precision, seriousness and foresight so that when slicing the bamboo which has been split and the inside removed can produce smooth, thin and even slices.

After the bamboo has been sliced into smooth and thin sections, the slices are then painted on the sections that will become part of the motif in making woven bamboo products. After several slices have been painted or colored, they are dried until the paint really sticks to the painted bamboo surface.

Nembeq is a term on the island of Lombok which means to weave or weave, the *nembeq* process is carried out after the bamboo processing has been completed and it is ready to make the woven process. Several sections of bamboo slices are taken by overlapping each other, namely the function of facing the craftsmen who use the two-axis weaving technique or often called the *Sasaq*, cross and single-woven weaving techniques. This weaving is done by crossing two axes. After the blades cross with other blades to form a crossed structure.

Some of the bamboo craft products produced in Loyok village, Sikur subdistrict include *Ponjol*, which is a container that is usually made from woven bamboo fibers which can be open at the top or can be closed with a lid. There are many uses for *ponjol* or basket. What is clear is that the first, as the name suggests, is as a place to store rice, the second as a place to wash rice before cooking, and the third can be used as a place to store various foods.

Figure 1 Ponjol

Next is Lompak, Lompak is a container used to store valuable items from people from the past until now in several villages in Lombok. These valuable items are money, necklaces, rings and/or others.

Figure 2 Jump

Dedungki is a container used to store fruit or food during nyongkolan events. In Sasak tradition, nyongkolan is a traditional activity that accompanies the wedding process of the Sasak tribe in Lombok, West Nusa Tenggara. This activity takes the form of a procession of the bride and groom from the groom's house to the bride's house, accompanied by the groom's family, relatives, wearing traditional clothes, as well as a musical troupe, namely a gamelan or group of tambourine musicians and accompanied by beleq drums.

Figure 3 Dedungki

4. Conclusion

Based on the research results and discussion in this research, it can be concluded that the types of products produced include Ponjol, Lompak and Dedungki. Next, the process of making bamboo crafts goes through the process of selecting bamboo and processing bamboo, including felling and cutting bamboo, slicing bamboo, painting and dividing bamboo slices, and *nembeq*.

For entrepreneurs or craftsmen to be able to develop woven bamboo crafts with more creative forms, techniques and functions and existing products to become more innovative products so that the results of woven bamboo production are not easily replaced by other products. beneficial. As well as being able to preserve bamboo woven crafts without abandoning the authenticity of the characteristics of bamboo processing.

For the woven bamboo craft industry in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok to further enrich the designs of woven bamboo crafts so that they are not monotonous, and create new designs that are more varied, creative, innovative, and high quality. For the woven bamboo craft industry in Loyok Village, Sikur, East Lombok, to expand its sales reach, it is recommended to create a website, block or social media for the sustainability of this business.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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